

THE USE OF ACTIVE AND INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE STUDY OF TURKISMS MASTERED IN RUSSIAN

Nasrullaev Jahongir Akhmadzhonovich

Teacher of the Russian language of the 33rd secondary school of Rishtan, Fergana region

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Abstract. *This article discusses the subject of the Russian language in secondary schools with national groups in Uzbekistan. We are talking about the use of active and interactive methods in teaching the Turkisms of the Russian language. The analysis of active and interactive methods is also mentioned.*

Keywords: *Russian language, Turkisms in Russian, lesson, interactive learning, interactive method, active learning method, cluster, brainstorming, project method, round table, presentation, verbal methods, story, conversation, lecture.*

The national program for personnel training, adopted in Uzbekistan, provides for a restructuring in the system of personnel training, taking into account world achievements in science, technology, and the integration of education.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in his speech noted: "It is necessary to focus on the education of young people, while strengthening the ideological immunity of student youth, educating them in high moral and human dignity" - having an independent worldview and independent thinking ... ". The head of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, argues that "we should talk more with young people, listen to their opinions, know what worries them, and provide practical assistance in solving problems," which, of course, is the main goal of the education system as a whole in the country.

One of the requirements of modern educational institutions for today's teachers is their educational process. Use and ability to apply proven in the world and effective active and interactive methods in teaching high school students. To do this, the teacher must constantly seek, learn and work on his knowledge, experiment with what he has learned. The teacher himself must be creative in his approach to these methods and it is necessary to make changes and additions. Until today, the use of verbal methods is common in educational institutions; it is a lecture, a story, a conversation, a personal consultation. Among the most popular and currently used modern teaching methods for high school students are: a lecture, a seminar, training, brainstorming and role-playing games.

Today it is necessary to consider the effectiveness and disadvantages of these modern active learning methods. The lecture is the most common method of teaching, which is an oral form of information transmission for students, during which visual aids are used. The advantages of a lecture are that it is possible to convey a large amount of information and teach a large number of students at the same time, and the teacher can easily control the content and sequence of his material. But the lecture should not be used in the primary grades of the school, because they cannot perceive such a large amount of material. The disadvantages of the lecture can also be attributed to the lack of feedback from students, there is no way to take into account knowledge and skills, and classes are strictly dependent on schedules and schedules. When studying the Turkisms of the Russian language, lectures do not give a definite result; students, when perceiving a huge amount of material, do not pay attention to the mastered words. And seminars may allow

us to achieve our goals. The seminar is a joint discussion between the teacher and students of the issues being studied and the search for ways and tasks. In seminars, one can raise the issue of the use of Turkisms in the Russian language and the peculiarities of their lexical meaning, establish a connection between the topic and the students' experience.

Let's talk about some active methods. When studying mastered Turkisms in Russian, the Cluster method gives a good result. For example, in the textbook of the sixth grade on the Russian language for schools of secondary education with Uzbek and other languages of instruction, published under the editorship of E. A. Khamrayeva, the text on page 48 is given for reading. In this text, the use of the word Turkisms such as hajja, teahouse, donkey, robe, kishlak, skullcap, caravan. Here the teacher, using his creativity to complete the task, can highlight the Turkic words using the "cluster" method. Such Turkisms are found in many pages of the textbook of the modern Russian language. You can take for example another informational text written about the city of Samarkand. In this text, there are a lot of Turkisms. For example, words such as Samarkand (name of the city), mosque (Muslim prayer architectural structure), madrasah (secondary or higher educational institution for the training of teachers and ministers of the Muslim cult), Registan (square in the center of Samarkand, meaning sand and place), mirzo (taken from the word murza-clerk), emir (ruler, leader), etc. Students will quickly recognize familiar words by pronunciation, and it will be interesting for them to highlight how they are pronounced in Russian. Although these words are non-equivalent vocabulary, their pronunciation in Russian varies phonetically and semantically.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, many Turkisms are actively used both in textbooks and in works of art for a deep realistic reflection of the life of the Uzbek people, their culture, way of life, customs, to create historical and national ethnographic color.

The very word "interactive" is an English word. It is formed from the words "inter" - "together" and "act" - "movement". Interactivity to move together or talk, something in a dialogue mode (e.g. computer) or be with someone (teacher). It follows that interactive education is, first of all, dialogical education, during which the teacher and the student interact. Interactive teaching methods are great for high school students, in order to use and enhance the educational power, competition in the educational process, allows you to introduce elements of the mental strength of a group of students.

Let's sum up the classification of interactive methods

1. What they study: call to the master, manufacturing methods
2. New material: understanding, methods
3. Learned: methods that make it possible to think:

Free writing. Cluster. Brainstorm. Figure B-B-B. Tangled logic sequence of chains. Blitz poll. Insert picture.

4. About learning guide:

Teach each other. Ask each other. Diaries in two parts.

The most basic concepts, repetition: T-chart. Classification table. Venn diagram.

5. Composition for five minutes and a ten-minute composition.

All these methods develop an interest in teaching in the teaching of almost all subjects taught in the general secondary education system and can be used, and, of course, well, if these methods are used correctly, then the result can be achieved. To do this, the teacher himself must be able to use his creativity, resourcefulness, skills and must have an idea about its application.

In Russian language lessons, these techniques are used in accordance with the age of the students.

Active and interactive methods should be used first in a simple form and then in a complex form.

Ways of understanding new material are mutually beneficial in mastering the science of cooperation, asking your teacher and friends about things that he did not know and did not understand before. These methods are not only considered effective, they develop both intellectual and educational value, that is, these methods form students' feelings of friendship, honesty, kindness.

Methods that allow students to reflect on what they have learned are new methods that measure how well they have mastered the subject.

Using them, students can think independently, assimilate knowledge, skills such as the ability to compare are formed.

Essay for five minutes.

Ten-minute essay.

develop skills such as drawing.

In the learning process, these methods are based on the purpose and content of the lesson.

development and implementation will lead to the following results:

- * the interest and motivation of students to study increases;
- * students are protected from boredom and fatigue in the classroom;
- * the student develops creative work skills and active thinking;
- * free and open involvement of new associative thoughts and imaginations on the topic helps to do.

In conclusion, language learning is a complex process for learners. counts. Students always face difficulties in learning the foreign languages they come to. The interactive methods we have listed above have the same difficulties. helps to exclude those who study foreign languages, especially Russian serves to increase their interest in mastering.

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